

Oxovanadium (IV & V) Complexes of Some Tridentate Schiff Bases

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Preparation and properties of some oxovanadium-(iv & v) complexes of dibasic tridentate Schiff bases derived by the condensation of 3-aldehydosalicylic acid with glycine (= ASAG-H₃) and anthranilic acid (= ASA-H₃) are described. The structures of the complexes have been discussed on the basis of elemental analyses, magnetic moments, infrared and electronic spectral data. The compounds [VO(ASAG-H)(H₂O)] and [VO(ASAA-H)(H₂O)] are found to be paramagnetic (μ_{eff} = 1.78 and 1.81 BM, respectively) and a square-pyramidal structure is assigned to them. The electronic spectra of these complexes are interpreted using recently proposed ordering of vanadium d orbitals by Vanquickenborne and McGlynn : $xy < xz, yz < x^2 - y^2 < z^2$. The other two compounds, [VO(ASAA-H)(OH)(H₂O)] and [VO(ASAG-H)(OH)]₂ are diamagnetic [and considered to be complexes of oxovanadium (V) species. These two compounds can easily be converted to the original oxovanadium (IV) complexes by grinding with sodium bisulphite in a little water. One broad but well defined absorption band is observed in the 10,000-25,000 cm⁻¹ region, which is attributed to ligand-metal charge transfer transition.

RECENTLY we have reported¹ some oxovanadium (IV) complexes of dibasic tetradentate Schiff bases. In this study we report the preparation and characterization of some oxovanadium (IV & V) complexes of dibasic tridentate Schiff bases derived from the condensation of 3-aldehydosalicylic acid with glycine (= ASAG-H₃) and anthranilic acid (= ASAA-H₃).

Experimental

The electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibilities were measured as described previously². The infrared spectra were recorded using KBr disk. Vanadium was estimated gravimetrically as pentoxide. Nitrogen was determined by the semimicro combustion technique. Solvents were purified and dried by usual procedures.

Preparation of the complexes :

[VO(ASAG-H₂O)] & [VO(ASAA-H)(H₂O)] : Amino acid (0.05 mole) and sodium acetate (0.1 mole) were dissolved in 80 ml. of distilled water by heating and then filtered. To the filtrate 3-aldehydosalicylic acid (0.05 mole) in 100 ml. of ethanol was added.

The mixture was stirred for 5 min and then oxovanadium (IV) dichloride dihydrate (0.09 mole) in 50 ml. of mixed solvent of ethanol-water (V/V) was added slowly with stirring. Within few minutes greyish brown precipitates were obtained. This was filtered, washed thoroughly with water, 50% ethanol and finally with ether. The compound was dried in vacuum desiccator.

[VO(ASAG-H)(H₂O)(py)] : Recrystallization of [VO(ASAG-H)(H₂O)] from pyridine gave this grey compound.

[VO(ASAA-H)(OH)(H₂O)] : The pre-formed Schiff base³, ASAA-H₃, was dissolved in calculated amount of the aqueous-ethanolic solution of sodium hydroxide and then mixed with stoichiometric amount of oxovanadium (IV) dichloride dihydrate and sodium acetate in ethanol (60 ml.) The mixture was refluxed on water-bath for about 2 hr and filtered. The brown filtrate yielded greenish brown compound on standing. This was filtered, washed with aqueous-alcohol and dried in air.

When [VO(ASAA-H)(OH)(H₂O)] was ground with sodium bisulphite in a little water the aquo-complex, [VO(ASAA-H)(H₂O)] was obtained.

[VO(ASAG-H)(OH)]₂ : The compound, [VO(ASAG-H)(H₂O)], was dissolved in boiling methanol and filtered while hot. The filtrate was then slowly evaporated to dryness on water-bath. The greenish brown compound, thus obtained, was washed with alcohol and ether and dried in vacuum desiccator.

Grinding this compound with sodium bisulphite in a little water gave back the original greyish-brown, [VO(ASAG-H)(H₂O)].

Results and Discussion

The compounds are coloured and sufficiently stable in atmospheric conditions for handling. The elemental analyses support the formulation of the isolated complexes (Table 1). All the complexes are soluble in dilute alkali solution, but decomposed by concentrated mineral acids and alkali solutions.

[VO(ASAG-H)(H₂O)] & [VO(ASAA-H)(H₂O)] : These two compounds are insoluble in ether, acetone and water, but slightly soluble in absolute methanol and completely so in pyridine. Both of them are paramagnetic and the magnetic moments (Table 1) are all close to the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. expected

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TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND $\nu_{\nu=0}$ OF OXOVANADIUM (IV & V) COMPLEXES OF SCHIFF BASES

No.	Complex	Colour	Calc. %		Found %		μ_{eff} (B.M.) Room temp.	$\nu_{\nu=0}$ (cm^{-1})
			V	N	V	N		
1.	[VO(ASAG-H)(H ₂ O)]	Greyish brown	16.66	4.57	16.05	4.81	1.81	992
2.	[VO(ASAG-H)(H ₂ O)(py)] ^a	Grey	13.24	7.27	13.52	7.38	1.77	968
3.	[VO(ASAA-H)(H ₂ O)]	Greyish brown	13.87	3.80	14.21	4.00	1.78	990
4.	[VO(ASAA-H)(OH)(H ₂ O)]	Greenish brown	13.24	3.63	13.39	3.71	Diamagnetic	968
5.	[VO(ASAG-H)(OH)] ₂	Greenish brown	16.66	4.57	16.53	4.62	Diamagnetic	970

a) py - pyridine.

for a d' system, which indicate that there are no appreciable interaction between the vanadium atoms. The $V = O$ stretching frequency is found to be about 990 cm^{-1} (Table 1) in KBr disk. But the solid pyridine adduct, [VO(ASAG-H)(H₂O)(py)], shows the $V = O$ stretching frequency at 968 cm^{-1} in KBr disk (Table 1). This lowering in $V = O$ stretching frequency in the pyridine adduct supports the five-coordination in the non-pyridine complexes isolated in the present study.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF [VO(ASAG-H)(H₂O)] IN NUJOL MULL AND IN PYRIDINE

	ν_{max} (cm^{-1})		ϵ_{max}	Tentative assignment
	Nujol mull	Pyridine solution		
One broad band in 13,000–17,000 region	12,880	14,350	31	$d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$
			38	
18,000	19,500	50	$d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$	
26,500	26,700	4850	Intraligand and charge transfer.	

The electronic spectra of [VO(ASAG-H)(H₂O)] is set out in table 2 along with their tentative assignments. The spectra of [VO(ASAA-H)(H₂O)] is of the same pattern. The spectral bands of these two complexes may be compared with those of VO(acac)₂ band, and may be considered as distorted square-pyramidal in structure. Three bands are observed in the region 12,000–27,000 cm^{-1} . The low-energy band is very broad and not well resolved into its components. The other two high energy bands are quite prominent, of which the third band is very intense.

Although the electronic spectra of the oxovanadium (IV) complexes are discussed at many places⁴⁻¹⁶, the assignments of observed electronic absorption bands for oxovanadium (IV) complexes has been a matter of controversy, most of the discussions are made in terms of C_{4v} and a few of C_{2v} symmetry. In C_{4v} symmetry three electronic transitions ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$; $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$; and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$) are theoretically expected for the d' oxovanadium (IV) ion¹⁶. The lowering of the symmetry from C_{4v} to C_{2v} or C_s has the effect of removing the degeneracy in the d -orbitals and thus four transitions are predicted. However, the two compounds mentioned

above show only three bands. Following the ordering of Vanquickenborne and McGlynn¹⁴ of the energy levels in oxovanadium (IV) complexes, the first band (Nujol mull) of the present complex, centered at $\sim 13,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, is assigned to an unresolved band resulting from $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$ transition. In pyridine two components with similar intensities ($\epsilon = 31, 38$) are observed as shown in table 2. Comparison of this band with the spectra of [VO(acac)₂] (loc. cit.) and [VO(Sal-L-alanine)(H₂O)]¹⁷ further support this assignment. The second band (Nujol mull), observed at $18,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, is attributed to the $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transition. This band appeared at $19,500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon = 50$) in pyridine solution. The high-energy shift of the second band and (slightly) low-energy shift of the first band agrees with the results noted for many oxovanadium (IV) complexes^{4,17}. We are less certain about the assignment of the third high-energy band observed at $26,780 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon = 4850$) in pyridine solution. This band may be considered to be due to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ transition buried under the highenergy charge transfer and intraligand transitions.

[VO(ASAA-H)(OH)(H₂O)]: This compound is insoluble in ether, acetone and water, but slightly soluble in hot methanol and completely soluble in hot pyridine. The compound is diamagnetic, which suggests that vanadium in this compound is in penta-valent state. The $V = O$ stretching frequency in this compound observed at 968 cm^{-1} , is 22 cm^{-1} lower than that observed for [VO(ASAA-H)(H₂O)]. But the difference in oxidation states of the metal in these two compounds prevents any meaningful interpretation.

Electronic spectra (Nujol mull) of this compound show a very broad (but intense) adsorption band at about $17,500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This may be due to ligand \rightarrow metal charge transfer transition. (see later part of the discussion).

When this diamagnetic compound was tritreated with sodium bisulphite in presence of little water a paramagnetic compound, identical with [VO(ASAA-H)(H₂O)], was isolated as identified by elemental analyses and magnetic moment value.

[VO(ASAG-H)(OH)]₂: When a methanolic solution of [VO(ASAG-H)(H₂O)] was slowly evaporated to dryness, a greenish-brown diamagnetic oxovanadium (V) complex was isolated. The complex is insoluble in common organic solvents, but soluble in boiling

pyridine. This greenish-brown diamagnetic compound can be easily converted to grey-brown paramagnetic form by grinding it with sodium bisulphite in a little water. This may be taken as another proof of the presence of pentavalent vanadium in the insoluble greenish brown compound. Though there is no direct evidence, the complex is formulated as a dimer on analogy with similar results obtained by other workers¹⁸.

The V = O stretching frequency observed in this dimeric compound at 970 cm⁻¹, is 22 cm⁻¹ lower than the V = O stretching frequency observed in the monomeric grey-brown compound. As mentioned above, the difference in oxidation states of vanadium in the two complexes prevents any meaningful interpretation. Similar results have been obtained by Silva. *et al.*¹⁸ with some oxovanadium (IV & V) complexes of N-Salicylideneaminoacids.

The electronic spectrum of this dimeric compound in nujol mull shows one broad (but prominent) band at about 17,000 cm⁻¹, which may be considered as the ligand → metal charge transfer transition¹⁹. We may mention here that the charge transfer should be lowest for oxovanadium (V) complexes, and the diamagnetism of the present dimeric complex is good evidence for the presence of pentavalent vanadium in the complex under discussion. Further, the formation of a monomeric oxovanadium (IV) complex with normal magnetic moment when ground with sodium bisulphite is another evidence for the presence of oxovanadium (V) species in the above dimeric complex. In a recent publication Theriot and co-workers²⁰ reported few dimeric oxovanadium (IV) complexes of the type [VO(Sal:AA)(H₂O)]₂, where Sal:AA are bivalent tridentate Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and various α-aminoacids. The sub-normal magnetic moments (*Ca.* 0.5 BM) of the compounds have been interpreted in terms of an antiferromagnetic interaction between the pairs of oxovanadium (IV) ions, and the absorption bands ~ 17,400–18,400 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon \sim 1500$) is

attributed to a *d-d* transition. This assignment is somewhat controversial¹⁸. If this long wave length band is considered to be charge transfer in origin [involving an oxovanadium (V) complex], which possibly reflect the presence of low-energy paramagnetic excited states, and would explain the large temperature independent paramagnetism of *Ca.* 0.5 BM observed by Theriot and co-workers²⁰.

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